

Strepsiptera

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HW Strepsiptera: Corioioxenidae *pc&c*

Triozocera mexicana

HW Strepsiptera: Halictophagidae

Coriophagus rieki

HW Strepsiptera: *Coriophagus rieki*

HW Strepsiptera: Halictophagidae

Coriophagus rieki

Mengenillidae: Mengenillia sp

RA and RP widely diverged at base as in Coleoptera

Mengenillia sp. 2.8 mm
 shows set entering pleura
 Shows MP dividing near base into MP 1+2 and MP 3+4 as in Coleoptera
 Shows CuA forced into cut 1+2 and cut 3+4 as in Coleoptera
 Shows SCP fused with anterior margin and well distant from DA Et radial bar is NOT forced 5

HW Strepsiptera: Myrmecolacidae

tegula reduced

CAENOCHOLAX FENYESI

Pierce, 1909

HW Strepsiptera = sistergroup of Coleoptera

Myrmecolacidae: *Lychnocolax* aff.

Lychnocolax

Lychnocolax 1.6 mm

Shows a short CuP - fused with AA as in Coleoptera (symapomorphy)